

Simulation-based inference in diffusion MRI: From uncertainty mapping to probabilistic tractography

J.P. Manzano Patron¹, Michael Deistler², Cornelius Schroeder², Theodore Kypraios³, Pedro Gonçalves^{2,4}, Jakob H. Macke², Stamatios N Sotiropoulos¹

¹Sir Peter Mansfield Imaging Centre, University of Nottingham, UK, ²Machine Learning in Science, Excellence Cluster Machine Learning, University of Tübingen & Tübingen AI Center, Germany, ³School of Mathematical Sciences, University of Nottingham, UK, ⁴VIB-Neuroelectronics Research Flanders (NERF), Belgium

Introduction: Uncertainty quantification in diffusion MRI (dMRI) provides a principled way of assessing confidence in the results [1], quantifying noise effects [2] and aiding experimental design [3]. Furthermore, uncertainty mapping for estimated fibre orientations provides the basis for white matter (WM) probabilistic tractography, generally done via bootstrapping [4] or Bayesian inference (MCMC) [5]. Simulation-based inference (SBI) [6] has emerged as a data-driven alternative that allows likelihood-free and amortized inference, thereby enabling a dramatic speed-up of inference on large datasets, while at the same time making it possible to tackle complex models. SBI is based on first training an artificial neural network (ANN) on simulated data to learn posterior distributions for unseen data (i.e., to amortise inference), avoiding repeated likelihood evaluations or expensive MCMC sampling. Recent studies have successfully explored the application of SBI into dMRI microstructural models [7,8,9]. Here, we extend these by exploring performance of SBI for mapping uncertainty of fibre orientation models and using it in probabilistic tractography of brain WM.

Methods: We developed an SBI framework for fitting the Ball&Sticks model [2] (N=2 crossing fibres). As shown in Fig. 1, SBI trains a Neural Posterior Estimator (NPE) [10,11] using synthetic data and learns the mapping between observations and the joint posterior distribution of the model parameters given the data. NPE can then be applied to estimate parameters and quantify their uncertainty on new unseen observations. We implemented and evaluated two different approaches:

Fig. 1 – Schematic representation of classical Bayesian inference (e.g., MCMC) and Simulation-based frameworks.

1) *SBI_joint*: a single NPE trained on both single- and crossing-fibre examples. 2) *SBI_classifier*: similar to [9,12], using the dMRI signal as input, a classifier first performs model selection and selects which of two NPEs trained independently (for N=1 and N=2, respectively) is employed. Both SBI approaches were trained with the default implementations in [13], with 6M and 1M samples, respectively. For the classifier, we implemented a Multi-Layer Perceptron (4 hidden layers of 256, 128, 64, 32 units, respectively, dropout and ReLu activation functions, SoftMax output, Cross-Entropy Loss, Adam optimization). We compared SBI against MCMC (with a sparsifying ARD prior on the volume fractions to enable online model selection [2]). We also assessed their ability to perform landmark-based probabilistic tractography [14] using data from a single-shell acquisition (50 directions, $b=2000$ s/mm²) [15].

Results and discussion: Fig. 2 shows a comparison of the estimates obtained from MCMC vs SBI, both in terms of mean estimates and their precision. Regarding the number of fibres predicted per voxel, both *SBI_classifier* and *SBI_joint* return similar patterns and rates of crossings to MCMC (~47%, 59%, and 51%, respectively). High agreement was also found in mean estimates maps for scalar parameters (such as volume fractions, Fig. 2A), as well as for mean 3D fibre orientation estimates (Fig. 2B). Similarly, similar patterns in the uncertainty of the estimated fibre orientations (Fig. 2c) were reproduced, with the SBI approaches returning slightly higher uncertainty (broader posterior) in some

WM areas. Differences with MCMC are slightly larger in *SBI_joint* than in *SBI_classifier*, potentially reflective of the more explicit model selection used in *SBI_classifier* and the MCMC.

Fig.2 – Comparison between the different methods in estimating A) the number of fibres per voxel and mean of the volume fraction posterior, B) mean of orientation posteriors (crossings in SLFs area), and C) uncertainty of fibre orientation posteriors (high uncertainty – bright, low uncertainty – dark).

We subsequently explored whether these small differences have an effect in probabilistic tractography. We used the fibre orientations and their uncertainties estimated by each method to reconstruct major white matter bundles. Fig. 3A shows the relevant comparison and the UKBiobank average tract atlas [13] as a reference. All methods were able to reconstruct all the bundle tracts successfully. Some false positives were observed (see arrows in Fig. 3A), but correlations against the UKB average atlas across tracts were reasonable and within the expected range [13]. Interestingly, SBI approaches achieved a better performance compared to MCMC (Fig. 3B). SBI estimates increased agreement in WM tractography reconstructions for the dataset employed here, against reconstructions obtained from better quality data, averaged across 1000 subjects.

Fig. 3 – A) Maximum Intensity Projections (MIPs) of tracts reconstructed by the different methods. The UK Biobank atlas (average of 1000 subjects) is shown as reference. B) Spatial tract correlation with the UKB average atlas.

Conclusion: Our results demonstrate the feasibility of using SBI for identifying and estimating fibre orientation in dMRI models, mapping calibrated uncertainty and use it subsequently for probabilistic tractography. SBI returned similar levels of accuracy and precision to MCMC with ARD priors. With orders-of-magnitude speedups in inference and greater flexibility in handling likelihood-free scenarios, our results highlight the potential SBI has in quantitative dMRI and modelling.

Acknowledgements: JP and SS are supported by an ERC Consolidator Grant (10100969), MD, CS and JHM by the German Research Foundation (DFG) through Germany’s Excellence Strategy (EXC-Number 2064/1, PN 390727645) and SFB1233 (PN 276693517), the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (Tübingen AI Center, FKZ: 01IS18039) the Carl Zeiss Foundation and the Else Kröner Fresenius Stiftung (Project ClinbrAIIn).

References

- [1]. Jones DK. Determining and visualizing uncertainty in estimates of fiber orientation from diffusion tensor MRI. *Magnet Reson Med*, 2003. 49(1):7–12
- [2]. Behrens TEJ, Woolrich MW, Jenkinson M, Johansen-Berg H, Nunes RG, et al. Characterization and propagation of uncertainty in diffusion-weighted MR imaging. *Magnet Reson Med*, 2003. 50(5):1077–88
- [3]. Alexander DC. A general framework for experiment design in diffusion MRI and its application in measuring direct tissue-microstructure features. *Magnet Reson Med*, 2008. 60(2):439–48
- [4]. Jones, DK. Tractography gone wild: probabilistic fibre tracking using the wild bootstrap with diffusion tensor MRI. *IEEE transactions on medical imaging*, 2008. Vol. 27, no.9, p. 1268-1274
- [5]. Behrens TEJ, Berg HJ, Jbabdi S, Rushworth MFS, Woolrich MW. Probabilistic diffusion tractography with multiple fibre orientations: What can we gain? *Neuroimage*, 2007, vol. 34, no 1, p. 144-155
- [6]. Cranmer K, Brehmer J, Louppe G. The frontier of simulation-based inference. *Proc National Acad Sci*. 2020. 117(48):30055–62
- [7]. Manzano-Patron JP, Kypraios T, Sotiropoulos, SN. Amortised inference in diffusion MRI biophysical models using artificial neural networks and simulation-based frameworks. *Proc. Intl. Soc. Mag. Reson. Med*. 30, 2022
- [8]. Jallais M, Palombo M. μ GUIDE: a framework for microstructure imaging via generalized uncertainty-driven inference using deep learning. arXiv:2312.17293 [physics], 2024
- [9]. Karimi HS, Pal A, Ning L., Rathi Y. Likelihood-free posterior estimation and uncertainty quantification for diffusion MRI models. *Imaging Neuroscience*, 2024. 2 1–22.
Doi: https://doi.org/10.1162/imag_a_00088
- [10]. Papamakarios G, Murray I. Fast ϵ -free inference of simulation models with bayesian conditional density estimation. *Advances in neural information processing systems*. 2016;29
- [11]. Greenberg D, Nonnenmache M, Macke J. Automatic posterior transformation for likelihood-free inference. *International Conference on Machine Learning*, 2019.
- [12]. Schröder, C, Macke, JH. Simultaneous identification of models and parameters of scientific simulators. arXiv:2305.15174 [cs], 2024.
- [13]. Tejero-Cantero A, Boelts J, Deistler M, Lueckmann J-M, Durkan C, et al. sbi: A toolkit for simulation-based inference. *J Open Source Softw*, 2020. 5(52):2505
- [14]. Warrington S, Bryant KL, Khrapitchev AA, Sallet J, Charquero-Ballester M, et al. XTRACT - Standardised protocols for automated tractography in the human and macaque brain. *Neuroimage* 2020. 217:116923

[15]. Manzano-Patron JP, Moeller S, Andersson JLR, Ugurbil K, Yacoub E, Sotiropoulos SN. Denoising Diffusion MRI: Considerations and implications for analysis. *Imaging Neuroscience*, 2024. https://doi.org/10.1162/imag_a_00060.